

UK PACT

GREEN RECOVERY
CHALLENGE FUND

UNIVERSITY
of York

Cin moriyar takaita sauyin
yanayi ta hanyar farfado da
bishiyoyin gargajiya ba tare da
ban ruwa ba: Salon bunkasa
ilimi da kwarewa

**KUNDIN INGANTATTUN
DABARUN AIKI**

**Domin amfanin kananan
manoma, kungiyoyin mata
da malaman gona**

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Yadda yakamata a ruwaito wannan talifin

Favretto N, Dallimer M, Stringer LC, Ado S, Baba Yakubu I, Jibrin JM, Barau A. 2021. *Harnessing benefits for climate change mitigation through irrigation-free indigenous tree restoration: sharing knowledge and building capacity. Best practice guidelines manual: Version for smallholder farmers, women's groups and extension officers.* UK and Nigeria: University of Leeds and Bayero University Kano.

Manufar shiri da tallafin gudnarda shi

An samar da wannan ingantaccen kundin jagora na horaswa karkashin hadin guiwa tsakanin jami'ar Bayero ta Kano Najeriya da Jami'ar Leeds da ta York a kasar Ingila. An samar da kudin tafiyar da wannan aiki karkashin tallafin shirin [UK PACT](#), **Green Recovery Challenge Fund** wanda ke da manufar farfado da dasa bishiyoyi domin horar da ma'aikata da zasu tallafi aikin dasa bishiyoyi da basa bukatar ban ruwa da kuma bishiyoyin gargajiya da aka gada kaka da kakanni a tsakkanin kananan manoma a arewacin Najeriya, da kuma rage fitar da iska mai barazana ga yanayi. Ta aiki tare da dukkan masu ruwa da tsaki a kowane mataki, hadakar zata tallafawa Najeriya dan ta cimma burinta na kaiwa gaci a fannin yin ayyuka masu dorewa da cimma muardun karni (SDGs). Nasarar wannan hadaka da ta shafi kasar noma da samar da abinci da yaki da dumamar yanayi ya dogara ne akan shigar da 'yan kasa cikin shirin. UK PACT ya samar da kudi kimnain Fam miliyan 60 daga Asusun Tallafawa Yaki da Sauyin Yanayi na ICF. Wanna tallafi kuma wani bangare ne na asusun da Birtaniya ta ware Fam biliyan biyar da miliyan 800 (£5.8bn) dan tallafawa asusun yaki da dumamar yanayi na duniya a shekarar 2021. Shirin kuma na samun kudinsa ne kai tsaye daga sashin bunkasa cinikayya da makamashi da masana'antu na kasar wanda akafi sani da Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy (BEIS).

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Shimfida

Yankin Arewacin Najeriya na fuskantar lalacewar kasar noma sakamakon sauyin yanayi da rashin tsarin amfani da kasar noma ta hanya mai dorewa. Akwai tsananin talauci a yankin, hadi da zaizayerar kasar noma dake haddasa kaura da fadace-fadace, da kin kula da hakkokin mata wadanda talauci yayiwa katutu, da rashin kasar da zasu noma. Mata na dogara da yin aikin hannu da kuma kwadago a cikin gonaki ga rashin kudi da horo da kuma hurumin fadar albarkacin baki. Gwamnatin Najeriya ta fifita tsarin sayen kayan amfanin gona daga hannun manoma da dogaro da tsarin yau da kullum na kula da shukoki da bishiyoyin da suka dade ana cin moriyarsu wadanda basa bukatar ban ruwa domin yaki da dumamar yanayi, da inganta rayuwar al'umma da rage yaduwar talauci ga kananan manoma dake zaune a yankunan karkara.

Domin isar da sako inda ya dace game da shirin farfado da dasa bishiyoyin gargajiya, wannan kundi ya tattara hanyoyi daban-daban mafi dacewa da za a tunkari dasa bishiyoyi da basa bukatar ban ruwa a fadin arewacin Najeriya. Yayi amfani da kasidu da aka samar da tarurruka na masana da sauran rahotannin bincike da aka gudanar a arewacin Najeriya. An samar da kundin ne daga bitoci da aka gudanar a jahohin Kano da Jigawa a cikin watan Agusta na 2021, daya sami halartar masu ruwa da tsaki da kungiyoyi daban-daban na manoma da mata da

shugabannin al'umma da masu maganin gargajiya da malaman gona da jami'an gwamnati. Bayan nanne kuma aka kara wani taron bitar a watan Satumbar 2021 inda masana suka yi nazari akan kudurorin da aka cimma a baya ta hanyar karbar shawarwarin masu ruwa da tsaki daban-daban.

An samar da wannan kundi hawa biyu. Wannan da ake magana akai, ya kunshi kananan manoma da mata da malaman gona daya maida hankali wajen koyar da aiki a zahiri. Daya kudin kuma na amfanin hukumomi ne masu bada tallafi da gwamnatoci da kungiyoyin kasa da kasa, ya kuma kunshi takaitaccen bayani na yawan kudin da ake kashewa da irin bishiyoyin da ake zaba a dasa da hanyoyin samar da kudin yin aikin da kuma tabbatar da dorewar tsare-tsaren farfado da bishiyoyi.

1 Gabatarwa

Wannan kundi zai gabatar da mataakai da hanyoyi na zahiri na gyaran bishiyoyin gargajiya da basa bukatar ban ruwa (sashi na biyu), da damammakin da ake dasu na inganta rayuwar al'umma mazauna karkara da karfafa sana'o'in al'umma masu rauni ta hanyar samar da kayan da zasu sayar da kayan da suke samarwa don fadada hanyoyin rayuwa daban-daban (sashi na uku).

Arewacin Najeriya wanda ya kunshi jihohin Kano da Jigawa na fama da lalacewar kasa da kwararowar hamada sakamakon dumamar yanayi da rashin kyakkyawan tsarin dorewar amfani da gonaki. Kusan kaso 70 cikin 100 na al'ummar yankin manoma ne kuma noma ne kashin bayan tattalin arzikinsu. Wannan ya zama tarnaki ga cigaban yankin. Yankin shine yafi kowane yanki a Najeriya yawan matalauta da lalacewar kasar noma ke haddasa kaura da fadace-fadace da dannewa mata hakkokinsu. Mata su suka fi fuskantar talauci, yayin da kuma tasirin rashin kyawun kasar noma ke taba rayuwarsu, saboda gudunmawarsu ta fuskar noma, yawancinsu kwadago kawai suke yi basu da kudi, basu da cikakken horo, kuma basu da ikon fada aji wajen masu zartar da kudurruka da suka shafi rayuwarsu kai tsaye.

Ma'aikatu a matakan gwamnatocin jihohi dana tarayya sun gano hanyoyin inganta yabanya da kuma farfado da dasa bishiyoyin gargajiya da basa bukatar ban ruwa, a

matsayin manyan hanyoyin yaki da dumanar yanayi da kawo karshen fitar da hayaki daga masana'antu da hanyoyin inganta rayuwar manoma a yankunan karkara, da kara yawan amfanin da ake samu a gonaki domin wadata kasa da abinci da rage radadin talauci. Farfado da dasa wadannan bishiyoyi wata sabuwar hanya ce da zata samar da kyakkyawan sakamako. Idan aka bita sannu a hankali zata taimaka wajen rage dumamar yanayi ta hanyar kara dasa bishiyoyi da inganta kasar noma da kyakkyawan yanayi mai yabanya da kuma inganta kasar noman kanta. Hanya ce kuma da zata bunkasa hanyoyin tattalin arziki da inganta muhalli, da samar da abinci domin amfanin bil adama da dabbobi da haifar da sabbin sana'oin da suka dogara kan aikin gona, don inganta rayuwar manoma da mata da al'umma masu rauni, da samar da makwanci da abinci don namun daji da sauran tsirrai da kwari da kuma samar da magungunan gargajiya.

2. Hanyoyin farfado da bishiyoyin gargajiya ba tare da ban ruwa ba

Wannan sashin ya zayyana mata kai uku na farfado da bishiyoyin da basa bukarar ban ruwa a arewacin Najeriya da za a iya farfado dasu a kowane irin yanayi domin amfanin al'umomi daban-daban, da za su yi amfani dasu karkashin kulawarsu.

Mataki na 1. Yadda za'a zabi tushiyoyin bishiyoyin da za'a farfado dasu

- Safiyo da gano bishiyoyi
- Fayyace bukatun mutane / da irin bishiyoyin da sukafi so
- Sanya alama akan bishiya da lanhon bishiyoyi

Mataki na 2. Rage yawan lanho da yiwa bishiya aski

Mataki 3. Bibiya don samun amfanin bishiyoyi

Zane na 1. Mata kai da za abi don farfado da bishiyoyin gargajiya ba tare da ban ruwa ba a Arewacin Nijeriya.

Mataki na 1. Yadda za'a zabi iri da lanhon bishiyoyin gargajiya

Mataki na farko da manomi zai dauka, shine tantance yawan bishiyoyin da zai raina a girman filin da yake dashi. Anayin haka ne da la'akari da bukatar wuri da kuma bada kulawa ta musamman ga mutane masu rauni a garin. Abin lura wajen zaben bishiyoyin da ake bukata domin farfado dasu, ya hada da mahimmancinsu da amfininsu (ko daya ne ko kuma nau'in alfanu mai yawa) da irin girman da ake tsammani zasu yi, da girman da suke dashi idan sun kai kololuwa, da kuma girman gonar da za a farfado dasu. Za'a kuma yi la'akari da matakin kariyar su (ko suna fuskantar barazana ko kuma hatsari). Wannan zai hada da matakai uku da za'abi kamar haka:

Safiyo and tantancewa

Manomi zai fara da gudanar da safiyo don gano nau'in bishiya. Manufar itace tantance adadi da kuma yadda yanayin bishiyoyin suke a yanzu (hoto na 2). Ya danganta da wane yanayi ake ciki kodai rani ko damina, watakila za a tarar babu wasu tsofaffin bishiyoyi da suka dade a wannan yankin, amma da zarar damina ta sauƙa sai ayi ta ganin lanho yana fitowa daga kasa.

Hoto 2. Safiyo don ganowa da tantance lanhon bishiya a wata gona kusa da Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.

Don saukin fahimta ga safiyon gano lanhuna, ansamar da jadawali (na daya) don ya nuna irin bishiyoyin da za abada misali dasu kamar yadda aka ganosu a jihohin Kano da Jigawa. Daga cikinsu manoma na iya zabe ta hanyar ilimin da suke dashi, da bishiyoyin da suka fi bukata, da bukatar al'ummar dake wannan yanki, da kuma samuwarsu. Sanin sunaye, ko takamaiman amfanin irin wadannan bishiyoyi ya banbanta daga gari zuwa gari. Amma idan aka tuntubi mata wadanda suke da kyakkyawar masaniya na amfanin bishiyoyi da kuma manyan gari da wasu masana zai taimaka wajen yin kyakkyawan safiyo da sanin amfanin kowace bishiya.

Jadawali na 1. Jerin sunayen bishiyoyin gargajiya da za'a farfado dasu a jihohin Kano da Jigawa a Najeriya kuma wannan ya hada da wuraren da suke, muhimman amfaninsu, da yadda da mutane masu rauni suke samun su. Wannan bishoshiyin sune wanda al'umma suka tattauna a kan su lokacin da akayi tarrurukan bita (a duba hotuna a Goya na 1).

Sunan bishiya na kimiyya	Sunan bishiya da Hausa	Wuri	Mihimmin amfanin su	Amfanin bishiyoyi da albarkatun su ga mata da masu rauni
<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	Bagaruwa	Kano and Jigawa	Gyaran kasa/yakar zizayar kasa, karo, icin girki.	Mata sunfi amfani da ice don girki, abincin dabbobi.
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Kuka	Kano and Jigawa	Abinci (ganye, dan ice, iri), magani (bawo don maganin basir), jijiya don rinin, bawon dan ince don girki a karkara, kayan gini. Adon gari.	Mata da yara sunfi amfani da ganye da dan ice.

<i>Anogeissus leiocarpus</i>	Marke	Kano and Jigawa	Makamashi, asuwaki, magani.	Amfanin al'umma.
<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	Aduwa	Kano and Jigawa	Magani, dan ice, icen girki, gyaran kasa, gyaran muhalli, gawayi, karo, mai.	Mata suna diban itace, yara suna diban 'ya'yan itacen.
<i>Butyrespermum parkii</i>	Kadanya	Kano and Jigawa	Man kadanya, icen girki, magani, ice da dan ice.	Mata na amfani da man kadanya don girki, itace.
<i>Cassia singuena</i>	Runhu	Jigawa	Magani (masu jego).	Mata ne suka fi amfani da ita saboda jego.
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	Rimi	Jigawa	Bwon bishiya, Ice, al'adu, magani (ganyen yana kara karfin maza).	Mata sun fi amfani da bawon bishiyar don yin katifa da matashi.

<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	Gawo	Kano and Jigawa	Gyaran kasa / zaizayar kasa, abincin dabbobi, ana shukashi cikin amfanin gona.	Mata sun ciro shi kuma su siyar da 'ya'yansa a kusawa.
<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Dorawa	Kano and Jigawa	Yakar zaizayar kasa, abincin dabbobi, daddawa, itace, magani (bawonta na maganin kuna da gudawa), alewa da gini.	Mata suna dauko itacen, kuma suna daddawa da 'ya'yan bishiyar.
<i>Piliostigma reticulatum</i>	Kalgo	Kano and Jigawa	Abinci (ana shan ganyen ta), magani, yakar zaizayar kasa da kuma abincin dabbobi.	Mata sunayin tsimin ta, irin ta kuma ana bwa dabbobi.

<i>Prosopis africana</i>	Kirya	Kano and Jigawa	Yakar zaizayar kasa, itace.	Mata na itacen girki da ita, maza kuma kanyi sanaoin hannu da ita.
<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Tsamiya	Kano and Jigawa	'Ya'yan itace, abincin dabbobi, yaki da zaizayar kasa, zuma, magunguna.	mata sun fi amfani da da 'ya'yan bishiyar
<i>Ziziphus spina-christii</i>	Kurna	Kano and Jigawa	Dan itace, magunguna, aikin gini, danga, gyaran muhalli, abincin dabbobi, zangon tsuntsaye.	Yara kan debo' ya'yanta su sayar a kasuwanni.

Tsara bukatun al'umma da shigar da harkokin mata da tantance Irin bishiyoyin da ake bukata

Bayan an kammala yin safiyo na irin bishiyoyin da ake dasu, sai kuma a zabi bishiyoyin da ake so ta hanyar tattaunawa tsakanin masu gonaki da kungiyoyin al'umma dake yankin, domin tabbatar da samar da wadanda al'umma suka fi bukata (nuni da hoto ko zane na uku). Farfado da rainon bishiyoyin gargajiya zai samar da hanyoyin neman abinci ya kara inganta irin bishiyoyin da ake dasu don habaka 'ya'yan da suke bayarwa da kuma amfanin da suke dashi wajen magani. Kamar yadda aka lura a wajen tarurrukan bita da aka yi, mata ne suka fi amfani da wadannan bishiyoyin ko 'ya'yansu. Don haka ya zama wajibi a karfafawa mata da sauran al'umma masu rauni wajen tattaunawa dasu domin jin ra'ayinsu, su kuma bada gudunmawa wajen bishiyoyin da aka zaba. Misali, a wani taron bita da aka yi a jihar Jigawa ra'ayin mata yafi karkata wajen rainon bishiyoyin dake samar da abinci. Zaman tattaunawar zai kai ga tantance bishiyoyin da aka fi bukata da cikakken bayani da amfanin da bishiyoyin suke ga bil adama idan aka yi la'akari da saukin samuwarsu ko kuma karancinsu. Kamar yadda taron bitar ya gano bayan anyi nazarin bukatun al'umma, yana da kyau a hari sakamakon da za a samu bayan shekaru masu yawa, ta la'akari da abubuwan da aka fi sayarwa a kasuwanni. Misali bada fifiko wajen rainon bishiyar Kadanya zai iya bunkasa yawan man kadanya da ake samu a kasuwar duniya.

Zane 3. Fitar da yadda al'umma suka tatauna wajen fitar da bishiyoyi da za a farfado da su a Jigawa. Wannan zane da Malama Kaltume Gana ta fitar: ita maizane ce, kuma tahalarci taron bitar da akayi.

Zaba da kuma sa alama a jikin daidaikun bishiyoyi da lanho da za'a farfado da su.

Bayan an fitar da irin bishiyoyin da mai gona da al'ummar gari suka fi bukatar a farfado da su, sai a ware wadanda suka fi tsawo, kuma mikakku a sa musu alama., sai kuma a sassake ragowar. Adadin tushe ko lanhon da aka zaba basa wuce shida zuwa goma a eka daya. Amma fa wannan ya danganta da irin tsarin kowace gona kamar yadda hoto na hudu (4) ya nuna.

Hoto na 4. Zaben lanhon da za'a ragewa yawa a garin Doka na Karamar Hukumar Tofa, Jihar Kano.

Mataki na Biyu: Rage yawa da aski

Bayan an zabi lanhon bishiyoyi, sai kuma a nome kewayen da bishiyoyin suke (hoto na 5), sai kuma a zabi sanduna da rassan da ba'a bukata (hoto na 6), sannan sare wadanda ba'a bukata (aski) (hoto na 7 da 8).

Hoto na 5: Manomi yana gyara gefen lanhon bishiyar *kargo* don rage yawan sanduna a Karamar hukumar Tofa, Jihar Kano.

Hoto na 6: Manomi yana zabar rassan da zai rage yawansu a Karamar Hukumar Gwale, Jihar Kano.

Hoto na 1: Manomi yana yanke bishiyar *Bagaruwa* a Karamar Hukumar Tofa

Hoto na 8. Bishiyar Bagaruwa da aka zaba a wata gona a Karmar Hukumar Tofa, Jihar Kano.

Kamar yadda aka tattauna a lokacin bita, kowane tushe na bishiya da aka zaba za'a rage sandunan a kuma bar kamar uku, sauran kuma a tattauresu sai amfanin gaba. Amma fa zabi ya ragewa manoma da kuma al'umma domin yayi daidai da bukatunsu. Manoma suna da damar zabar yawan lanhon da zasu raina akan kowace eka. Misali a taron bita da aka yi a jihar Jigawa, an gano cewa idan za'a dasa Kalgo za a bar sanda daya. Ayi amfani da sanayyar da ake da ita ta irin bishiyoyi zai taimaka wajen tabbatar da cewa anyi shirin da zai bada kyakkyawan sakamako. Ayi amfani da abu mai kaifi wajen gyaran lahon da za'a bari su farfado kuma a gyaran saman sosai

maimakon kasa don a rage asarar da za'a samu wajen cire sassake da kuma girman bishiyar akan lokaci.

Mataki na 3: Bada kariya da kuma cin moriyar bishiyoyin da aka raina

An fahimci cewa a Jihohin Kano da Jigawa, dabbobi sukan ci ganyayyaki na bishiyoyin gargajiya, don haka kiwon dabbobi na yin barazana ga girman irin wadannan bishiyoyi da kuma sake farfado dasu. Bisa haka ake shawartar al'umma su billo da dokoki da hanyoyin da za'a killace dabbobi don kar su barnatar da irin wadannan bishiyoyin. Kazalika, yana da kyau a rika zama da makiyaya ana wayar masu da kai musamman bakin makiyaya don su fahimci tanade-tanaden da dokokin suka kunsu.

Yana da kyau a kare bishiyoyin yayin da suke girma. Kuma a hana dabbobi cinyesu da karesu daga wutar daji da sauran tsirrai masu mamaya . Za'a iya yin haka ta hanyar samar da kandagarki na hana gobarar daji kaiwa ga bishiyoyi ko yin shingayen kaya da zasu hana dabbobi yin kutse. Kamar yadda aka amince a bitocin da aka yi, za'a iya amfani da bishiyoyin Bini-da-Zugu domin yin irin wadannan shingaye.

Yana da muhimmanci kowane watanni biyu zuwa shida a rika gewaya, domin sassare hakukuwa da sauran ciyayi da

rassan da ba'a bukata, hakan zai sa bishiya ta girma da wuri kuma da mike (hoto na 9).

Hoto na 9. Sabon lanhon Kalgo a Chai Chai, Karamar Hukumar Ringim a Jihar Jigawa.

Za'a iya rage rassa har su zamo adadin biyu bisa uku na rassan dake jikin bishiya idan ta kara tsawo fiye da mita biyu. La'akari da yadda al'ummar gari suka amince da kuma irin bukatunsu da yadda suke kula da bishiyoyin za'a iya amfani da wannan tsari daidai da yadda masu gonaki suke bukata. Misali idan bishiyoyi suna girma ne a cikin gonaki da aka shuka amfanin gona akwai bukatar sassabe daga lokaci zuwa lokaci don rage yawan inuwa da zata cutar da amfanin gona. A bitar da aka yi a jihar Jigawa

cikin kudurin da aka amince dashi shine muhimmancin tabbatar da cewa mata su rika amfani da itatuwan da ba 'a katako dasu. Misali bayan amfani da wadansu 'ya'yan itatuwa da mata ke yi domin ciyar da dabbobi, sukan yi kuma amfani dasu ta wadansu hanyoyin kamar diban gayayyaki da kayan marmari domin amfani kamar yadda aka zayyana a jadawalin farko na wannan kundi.

La'akari da yadda aka tsara yin amfani da bishiyoyin tsakanin al'ummar gari, a iya karkasa amfanin kamar haka:

- i. Akan iya sassare rassan bishiyoyin lokaci zuwa lokaci domin yin girki ko samar da taki ko samar da abincin dabbobi ko don yin magani dasu. (hoto na 10).
- ii. Ko a yiwa bishiyoyin kundumi, ko kuma
- iii. A kyale bishiyoyin yadda suke domin samar da amfani mai dorewa.

Hoto na 10. Rage yawan rasan bishiya na iya zama wata hanya mai dorewa da za'a iya samar da itacen girki kamar yadda aka nuna a Sugungun ta Karamar Hukumar Garki, ta Jihar Jigawa.

Kowace hanyar da akayi amfani da ita zata iya samar da alfanu da wasu damar bunkasar hanyoyin rayuwa daban daban da masu amfani da filayen noma da kuma al'umma (a duba sashi na 3).

AKWATU 1.

Abubuwan da aka duba: Hanyoyin gyara da kulawa

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3. Alfannun bishiyoyin gargajiya a tsarin hada noma da rainon bishiyoyi

Yawan dasa bishiyoyi yana rage barazanar sauyin yanayi musamman ga kananan manoma wajen samar da hanyoyin gudanar da aikinsu da kuma basu damar tsallake kowane irin yanayi kamar fari ko ambaliyar ruwa. Idan aka bi mata kai na tsanaki, bishiyoyin gargajiya suna samar da hanyoyin tattalin arziki da inganta muhalli. Amfanin su ya hada da karuwar amfanin gona da ake samu da abincin dabbobi, inganta tattalin arzikin kananan manoma, da abinci ga namun daji da samar da kyakkyawan yanayi domin rayuwar tsirrai da sauran

kwaruka da kuma samar da maganin gargajiya a saukake. Bitocin da aka yi sun maida hankali wajen rainon bishiyoyi don samar da kudin shiga da inganta tattalin arzikin mata ta hanyar sayar da itace da sarrafa kayan marmari da ake samu daga bishiyoyi da kuma 'ya'ya da ganyayyaki na bishiyoyin da ake amfani dasu a sarrafa su zama kayan abinci kona dandano da lemuka da kayan shayi da sauran kayan masarufi na yau da kullum. Kazalika ana samar da tabarmi da kwanduna daga gayayyakin wadannan bishiyoyi, (Zane na 11). Sakamakon bitocin ya nuna cewa rainon bishiyoyi yana bada wani alfanu ta fuskar addini. Kamar yadda yake a Musulunci, rainon bishiya da bata kulawa har zuwa girman ta sadaka ce mai gudana dake samar da lada ga wanda ya assasa al'amarin har bayan rayuwarsa.

Zane na 11. Mata na dauke da kayan marmari daga bishiyoyin gargajiya da aka farfado da su a Kano. Malama Kaltume Gana: mai zane ce, manomiya, kuma ta halarci bitar da akayi.

Idan ana duba irin alfanu da aka zayyana a sashi na biyu na wannan kundi, mahalarta bita sun fahimci cewa za a iya shawo kan dumamar yanayi ta hanyoyi da dama musamman ma abinda ya shafi rage iska mai dumama yanay. Bishiyoyi suna da jijiyoyi masu tsawo a kasa wadanda ke hana ambaliyar ruwa a lokacin damuna ta hanyar tsotse shi su kuma bada damar fitar da ruwan daga kasa a lokacin rani. Ba kamar hatsi da ake shuka shi lokaci zuwa lokaci ba, da dabbobi da suke da lokacin da suka fi bada amfani, bishiyoyi Allah ya basu baiwa ta rike danshi da fitar da tururi tsawon lokaci kuma suna jurewa Fari da ambaliya. Kazalika bishiyoyin da ake dasu tsawon

lokaci suna taimakawa kasar noma ta hanyar rike ruwa da muhimman sinadaran da kasar noma ke bukata. Don haka matakan da aka zayyana a cikin wannan kundi a iya amfani dasu wajen rage dumamar yanayi da kasha suka sa a gaba.

Wasu Karin alfanunnun dake tattare da farfado da bihiyoyin 'yan ksa ya hada da wandannan:

- Suna kawata gari kuma ja hankalin masu yawon bude idanu. Kafa gandun daji na tsofaffin bishiyoyi suna rangaji kamar su Kuka na daukar hankali masu yawon bude idanu.
- Suna bada damar cin gajiyar kasar noma mai yawan gaske
- Suna hana karewar tsofaffin bishiyoyi
- Yin amfani da bishiyoyi wajen shata iyakar gonaki yana rage rikicin mallaka
- Suna taimakawa wajen inganta sinadarin iskar Nitrogen
- Ana amfani dasu musamman wajen hana kwararowar hamada

Domin cin gajiyar wadannan alfanu da aka zayyana a sama, ayi duba na tsanaki akan abin da aka zayyana a wannan kundi don yin amfani dasu tare da sauran shirye-shiryen bunkasa aikin gona da bai tsaya kawai kan kula da bishiyoyi ba, kamar bunkasa gandun daji dan samar da hanyoyin fadada tattalin arziki da yalwar abinci tsakanin kananan manoma a Najeriya. Shigar da mata da basu

daidaito cikin wannan tsari yana da mahimmancin gaske saboda matan karkara zasu iya samar da hanyoyin yalwata abinci su samu karin hanyoyin samun kudi. Misali da hanyar debo itacen siyarwa domin girki. Tsari ne da yake karawa mata karsashi ya kuma amfani kananan manoma su sami cikakken amfanin fafutukar da suke ta yau da kullum da samun damar mallakar kadarori da karuwar hanyoyin kudin shiga da dasa bishiyoyin da basa bukatar ban ruwa da bunkasa hanyoyin noma masu dorewa, duk manyan hanyoyi ne na dogaro da kai.

Tsarin rainon bishiyoyi a filayen noma yana samar da yalwar abinci ya kuma daga matsayin tattalin arziki da ingantaccen muhalli ta hanyar inganta yanayi da magance zaizayar kasa da rage radadin dumamar yanayi da samar da kyakkyawan yanayi da kwari da sauran tsirrai zasu rayu. Tsarin noman hadaka yana bada kayan abinci daban-daban da wanda ake siyarwa da samar da abincin dabbobi da sauran kayayyakin bukату kamar katako da sinadarai da gayayyakin da ake magani dasu da kuma kirare domin girka abinci. Tsarin yana inganta yabanya koda akwai karancin ruwa, ta hanyar bada tazara yayin shuka don shukoki su sami danshin da suke bukata, su iya jure kowane irin yanayi na fari (hoto na 12).

Hoto na 12. Wasu kayan gona a karashin bishiyar Tsamiya a karmar hukumar Bebeji a Jihar Kano

Koda yake tsarin rainon bishiyoyi a cikin gonaki yana taimakawa kananan manoma da mata da mutane masu rauni wajen fadada masu yawan amfanin da suke samu, da samar da karin kudin shiga. Ya kamata ayi la'akari da cewa nasarar wannan tsarin ya dogara ne akan yanayin

da aka samu kai. Matakan da za a bi wajen cimma nasarar wannan tsari sunanan a hoto na 13, yayin da cikakken bayani game da hakan yana nan zayyane a akwati na 2:

1. Yanke shawarar rainon bishiyoyi a cikin gona:

- Zabar irin bishiyoyin da za'a raina, a ina da kuma lokacin da yadace
 - Yadda za a gudanar da ayyuka

2. Abubuwan da za a samar daga gonakin noma tare da bishiyoyi

- Hidimomi (rage dumamar yanayi, kare zaizayar kasa, taimakon hallittu, etc.)
- Kaya (katako, itacen girki, abinci, abincin dabbobi, magani.)

3. Shawarar yadda za a ci gajiyar abin da aka samu

- Amfanin yau da kullum
- Sarrafawa domin a siyar
 - Gano sabbin amfanin da za a sarrafa
 - Tantance kudin da aka kashe da wadanda za a yi Jari dasu
- Tallatawa
 - Sarrafa amfani da samar da kasuwa
 - Samun cikakken bayanin irin kasuwannin da za a kai kaya domin sayarwa
 - Samun kwarewa da dabarun tafiyar da tsarin

Zane na 13. Muhimman mata kai da za bi son aiwatar da aikin noma tare da farfado bishiyoyi na gargajiya.

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Annex I. Goyo na 1. Hotunan bishiyoyin gargajiya iri-iri da za a iya farfado da su a Jihohin Kano da Jigawa na Nijeriya a sanya su a Tebur na 1.

Acacia nilotica (Gabaruwa)

Adansonia digitata (Kuka)

Anogeissus leiocarpus (Marke)

Balanites aegyptiaca (Aduwa)

Butyrespermum parkii (Kadanya)

Cassia singuena (Runhu)

Ceiba pentandra (Rimi)

Faidherbia albida (Gawo)

Parkia biglobosa (Dorawa)

Piliostigma reticulatum (Kargo)

Prosopis africana (Kirya)

Ziziphus spina-christii (Kurna)

